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Role of TMEM230 in the Aberrant Glycosylation in Human Autoimmunity and Cancer

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ABSTRACT

Alterations in glycoconjugate profiles are thought to promote changes in cell-to-cell and cell-to-intracellular and extracellular scaffold interactions in human disease. The nearly unlimited number of “glycoforms” that may exist in nature are difficult to study due to glycosylation and glycoconjugate modifications being associated with non-genome coded posttranscription and post-translation processes. Specific products generated by glycosylation are dependent on concentration and sub-cellular locations of glycan synthesis and processing enzymes. An indirect “high-throughput” approach to study glycosylation is to characterize glycan processing enzymes (hydrolases and transferases) by single cell sequencing of all cell types in tissue of human diseases. We previously identified TMEM230 as an endoplasmic reticulum (ER) associated protein that regulates NOTCH glycoprotein receptor and ligand signaling in zebrafish blood vessel formation and destructive remodeling capacities of diverse cell types including fibroblast, phagocytic and immune system cells in patients with cancer or granulomatous systemic vasculitis autoimmune disorder. NOTCH signaling represents a paradigm in glycan mediated signal transduction and supports the role of TMEM230 in glycan modifications. The ER initiates the earliest steps of glycoconjugate synthesis, sorting, and trafficking. As blood vessel and tissue remodeling, and Notch signaling are hallmarks of autoimmune disorders, we investigated whether aberrant TMEM230 expression was also associated with changes in expression of glycan processing enzymes in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA). In this current study, single cell sequencing analysis supported that TMEM230 expression was downregulated in all cell types associated with synovial tissue of RA patients while glycan processing enzymes were predominantly upregulated. In contrast, TMEM230 was upregulated in patients with high-grade compared to low-grade gliomas as it was N-linked glycosylation (GlcNAc), and glycoprotein and glycosaminoglycan expression. Our collective results support that TMEM230 regulates glycan/glycoconjugate processing enzymes in RA and the expression of protein glycoconjugate

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in aggressive gliomas. TMEM230 may therefore be a therapeutic target and marker for clinical treatment for glycosylation induced human autoimmunity disorders or cancer.

1 | Introduction

The endomembrane system (ES) includes membrane bound organelles, endoplasmic reticulum (ER), the Golgi complex and lysosomes that allow for compartmentalized synthesis and turnover of glycoconjugates [1–8]. Essential to the ES are the intracellular scaffolds/cytoskeleton for trafficking of glycoconjugate cargo between the sub-cellular membrane bound structures and non-membrane bound bodies, and the secretion of factors and vesicles necessary for cells to interact, modify and modulate their extracellular environment. The ES and intracellular network of scaffolds distinguish eukaryotes from prokaryotes [2, 9, 10]. The evolution of metazoans required ability of different cell types to interact for tissue development and multicellular host organisms to defend themselves from pathogens. The ability for cells, extracellular matrix and host-pathogen interactions are due to glycans as glycans have a nearly unlimited number of combinatorial structural and linear forms. The possibilities of form are generated and modified by a variety of competing and sequentially acting glycosidases and glycosyltransferases in sub-compartmentalized “assembly-line” sequential steps of glycan biosynthesis in the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus [1, 7, 8, 11]. Additionally, glycosylation provides a molecular system for the degradation or turnover of cellular components that are damaged or of non-functional value to the cells. For instance, cellular factor modification with mannose 6-phosphate (Man-6-P) is associated with the intracellular trafficking of lysosomal degradation by enzymes (for instance, RNASET2) such as in cell starvation or regeneration (following injury or disease) of organelles and plasma membrane of the endomembrane system [3, 12–14]. Surprisingly, glycan and glycoconjugate diversity are not coded into the genome of cells but are generated as glycoconjugates [3, 4, 15, 16]. Rather, compartmentalization of glycosylation processing enzymes generates the tremendous diversity, for instance necessary for cell-to-cell interactions (intrinsic recognition) and host to pathogen evasion (extrinsic recognition). This diversity contributes to the innate and adaptive immune systems [17, 18] and the formation and regeneration of the endomembrane system of organelles and plasma membrane of the endomembrane system [19–21].

It has been reported that loss of normal glycan and glycoconjugate formation and processing in cells contribute to cancer and autoimmune disease development [13, 16, 22–25]. In multicellular organisms, cancer in part is due to tumor cells that fail to maintain contact inhibition within tissue boundaries demarcated by different cell types and scaffolds. Contact inhibition in part is due to proper recognition of glycoconjugates on cell membranes and in the extracellular environment. Oncogenesis may also be due to inability of an organism to recognize immunologically rogue acting cells that have loss specific glycoconjugate molecules on their plasma membranes or due to remodeling of the glycan containing extracellular matrix [26–30]. Change in tissue morphology in cancer may be

observed as a loss of multicellularity associated with glycan function and an evolutionary reversion towards a unicellular-like state. Many genes responsible for the establishment of multicellularity are mis regulated in cancer cells, including genes that control of the endomembrane system and intracellular cargo trafficking, necessary to maintain glycan dependent cell-to-cell, cell-to-matrix substrate, and immune system interactions [31]. Glycan synthesis and processing is initiated in the ER [23]. The carbohydrate part of glycoconjugates plays an important role in the function of the ER-dependent glycan processing enzymes that leads to loss of intrinsic recognition of host cell with immune system cells and host-pathogen extrinsic recognition, promoting in addition to cancer, also auto-immunity disease or infection [32]. The exact causes of auto-immune diseases remain largely unknown. However, research has suggested that a combination of genetic, and environmental factors, as well as certain infections, may contribute to the development of human disorders, and T and B cells can react with self-proteins [16, 18, 33–36]. In a healthy immune response, self-reactive cells are generally destroyed and eliminated before they become active, made un-reactive by anergy, or suppressed by other regulatory cells. In healthy individuals, immune tolerance prevents the immune system from attacking the body's own cells. When this process fails, the immune system may produce antibodies against its own tissues, leading to an auto-immune response.

The altered “glycan theory” in autoimmunity posits that autoimmunity is due to alterations in glycosylation profiles of cells such that a pro-inflammatory immune response is promoted [13, 18, 25]. Therefore, individuals with autoimmune disease have unique glycan signatures compared to healthy patients. Glycan modifying enzyme and motor proteins are essential for the activation of the immune system by trafficking of antigens between the endomembrane system and the plasma membrane [9, 34, 36]. We previously have shown that TMEM230, an ER associated protein regulates the ES with ATP powered motor protein trafficking of intracellular cargo and secretion [1, 9]. More recently, we demonstrated that TMEM230 was down-regulated in RA compared to osteoarthritis (OA) patients [9].

As glycan and glycoconjugate diversity are not coded into the genome of cells in this study, by comparing single cell sequencing transcription profiles of samples obtained from patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) or osteoarthritis (OA) (used as control) we investigated and determined that glycan processing enzymes are differentially expressed and therefore create altered glycosylation profiles that distinguishes RA from OA cells. We found that in RA patient cells glycan processing enzymes were predominantly upregulated in immune system, blood vessel and synovial fibroblast cells compared to OA. Previously we also found that TMEM230 was upregulated in aggressive gliomas and glioblastoma (GBM) compared to low grade gliomas (LGG) [1, 2, 37]. TMEM230 modulated the cellular activities of endothelial (EC) and tumor phagocytic glial

cells resulting aberrant blood vessel growth and destructive or disease inducing extracellular matrix remodeling. Aberrant blood vessel growth and synovial cell promoted tissue remodeling are also pathological features in RA. Our new study also suggests that in cancer TMEM230 and MHC class II glycoprotein molecules are upregulated and that TMEM230 may have a role in aberrant immune system regulation in cancer. This contrasts with RA patients where TMEM230 expression is absent or very low in immune system MHC class II expressing cells such as professional antigen presenting macrophage, dendritic cell, immune cells. Our analysis indicated that TMEM230 is a marker in autoimmune diseases and cancer development.

2 | Background

We previously identified *tmem230*, a transmembrane protein of the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) as a master regulator of angiogenesis in early zebrafish development [38]. *tmem230* in zebrafish controls the number and migration of the endothelial cells (ECs) in intersegmental vessels by controlling the interactions of the components of the Delta/Notch and Vegf signaling pathways. The Notch receptor and Notch ligands Delta and Serrate/Jagged are glycoproteins that contain epidermal growth factor (EGF)-like repeats which are post-translationally modified by glycans [29, 33, 39]. In human, the Notch receptors are a family of transmembrane proteins that mediate direct cell-cell interactions and control numerous cell-fate specifications. Inactivation of glycosyltransferases which initiate and elongate these glycans inhibits Notch signaling and normal angiogenesis. The regulation of Notch signaling by glycans represents a paradigm of glycan mediated signal transduction [40–44]. Our early research demonstrated that modulation of *tmem230* expression by itself was sufficient to rescue improper number of ECs induced by aberrant expression or inhibition of the activity of genes associated with the Notch receptor and ligand glycoprotein pathway in zebrafish [38]. How TMEM230 modulates vessel-network formation in early vascular development and in wound healing became a focus of our continuing research. The ER mediates the earliest processes in glycan synthesis and glycan conjugation to proteins, lipids and carbohydrates [3, 4, 15]. Glycans have diverse roles including proper folding, stability, solubility of proteins and therefore are essential in intracellular trafficking to organelles and to plasma membrane and in secretion of cell factors [1, 4, 8]. Concurrent to our studies, specific human gene mutations were identified promoting aberrant TMEM230 protein structure formation in Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD) [45–47]. Subsequently, these gene mutations were not demonstrated as etiologic, suggesting a more general role of TMEM230 in ER regulation in PD and AD, such as in protein stability or quality control in the synthesis of proteins in Lewy bodies (LBs) [48–51]. Another proposed role of TMEM230 was the regulation of cell death by selective autophagy of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in the substantia nigra due to ER mediating protein or glycan associated factor in stress response. Proteins destined for the plasma membrane (such as glycoproteins), or secretion (proteoglycans) are generated by ribosomes that are docked to

the rough ER. As the proteins are synthesized, they are simultaneously translocated into the ER lumen where they are then glycosylated and undergo proper protein folding by diverse chaperones [3, 6, 15, 23, 43, 52–55]. Misfolded or otherwise aberrant proteins are identified by quality control processes in the ER and retrotranslocated by ER-associated degradation (ERAD) by proteasome complexes for proteolysis in the cytosol [54, 55]. ERAD targets misfolded proteins of the ER for ubiquitination. Significantly, recognition of misfolded or mutated proteins depends in part on the glycans that are conjugated to the proteins that promote the detection of substructures within proteins such as exposed hydrophobic regions or immature glycans. The role of glycans in ER dependent protein folding and stability and ER stress is important in protecting or inducing unfavorable physiological or pathological conditions. It occurs upon the accumulation of misfolded or unfolded proteins in the ER. As a result, ER plays a pivotal role in the development of many neurodegenerative disorders, including Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases [46].

Candidate roles of TMEM230 in ER regulation and glycan processing in cancer and RA were supported by our previous studies demonstrating that TMEM230 promoted angiogenesis and destructive tissue remodeling by inducing sprouting and tubule-like structures in human endothelial derived cells cocultured with human cell lines (U-87-MG) that recapitulate tumor features associated with high-grade gliomas [19–21, 56–58]. Vessel-like structures by phagocytic (fibroblast and macrophages) and tumor glial cells themselves through a process described as vascular mimicry were promoted by TMEM230 upregulation [1, 2, 37]. Additionally, when TMEM230 was down regulated in human tumor cells or ECs, these cells lost the ability for substratum adhesion and consequently, substrate dependent motility and survival [37]. Control tumor cells expressing TMEM230 displayed significant increase in migration capacity and when confronted with ECs in their path in coculture assays, infiltrated, enveloped or displaced ECs suggestive of the intussusceptive structural remodeling of blood vessels, leading to new vessel branching. Therefore, TMEM230 appears to have the capacity to increase tissue vascularization, remodel the tumor tissue microenvironment and extracellular glycoconjugated scaffolds. These features are hallmarks for cancer and RA development [59]. Cell adhesion modulated by ECM and glycosylated membrane proteins are essential for cell attachment to basement membrane and extracellular matrix components to allow migration and remodeling of the microenvironment. Our previous gene expression analysis uncovered specific pathways associated with the increase of TMEM230 expression in pathways involved in cell adhesion, secretion, and membrane regulation, angiogenesis, response to hypoxia, endocytic vesicle membrane and exosome vesicle regulation, and lysosome and phagosome activities [1, 9]. Highest levels of TMEM230 upregulation were identified with increase expression of proteins associated with mitochondrial structure and activities, and ATP dependent microtubule motor activity (kinesin motor proteins) necessary for ER dependent intracellular trafficking and secretion of glycan containing scaffolds. Abnormal glycosylation is a typical hallmark of the transition from healthy to neoplastic tissues and was

reported for RA [22, 24, 30, 41, 42, 60, 61]. Although the importance of glycans and glycan-binding proteins in cancer-related processes such as tumor cell adhesion, migration, metastasis, and immune escape has been previously described, our recent discovery that TMEM230 may promote tumor vascularization (angiogenesis and tumor cell promoted micro channeling) and ECM associated glycoconjugated scaffold remodeling is relatively new [1, 9]. Regulated glycosylation can influence vascular biology by controlling trafficking, endocytosis, and signaling of EC receptors including vascular endothelial growth factor receptors, platelet EC adhesion molecules, NOTCH, and integrins [1, 9]. In addition, glycans may control angiogenesis by regulating migration of endothelial tip cells and influencing EC survival and vascular permeability [1, 9]. Recent evidence also indicated that changes in the glycomic surface composition of ECs such as proteins that bind to glycans, as galectin may act as regulatory switches [62]. Glycosylation-dependent lectin-receptor interactions are associated with tumor hypoxia to EC signaling and contribute to changes in tumor sensitivity to therapeutic treatments [63].

Our long-term research focuses on identifying ER dependent activities of TMEM230 in regulation of glycosylation modulating processes in human disease, including cancer and autoimmunity-based cells processes.

3 | Methods

3.1 | Glioblastoma Patient Data Collection for Transcriptomic Analysis

mRNAseq datasets and corresponding patient clinical data were obtained from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) (Cancer Genome Atlas Research Network). Samples included for analysis were 172 from patients with high-grade (G3, G4) glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), 198 from patients with oligodendroglioma and 197 from patients with astrocytoma. Grades of tumors were defined according to the American Joint Committee on Cancer, AJCC, as previously described [37].

3.2 | Glioblastoma Patient Rna-Seq Gene Expression Analysis

Transcriptomic profiling of genes in different gliomas was performed using R package TCGA2STAT V 5.2.3 and normalized with RSEM [64, 65]. The samples were divided into TMEM230 high and TMEM230 low based on TMEM230 expression level. Differentially expressed genes associated with increased glioma tumor grade were identified in LGG and HGG patient datasets using p-values and log₂ FC, as described in each table. Gene ontology and biological pathways were assessed using the False Discovery Rate method (Benjamini) [66, 67]. Differential gene expression analysis was performed using DESEQ. 2 R package (version 1.30.1) with a p-value cut-off < 0.05 and an absolute log₂ fold change cut-off > 0.58 as previously described [37]. Functional enrichment analysis was performed using DAVID (version 6.8) [68, 69].

3.3 | Glycosylation Enzyme Gene Expression in RA Versus OA Clusters Generated by Single Cell RNA Seq Analysis

The different cell populations from OA and RA were analysed by comparing the different cell cluster one to each other using Gene Set Enrichment Analysis from 15 DEGs lists as previously described [37]. A total of 363 Human Glycosylation Enzyme encoding genes were collected from the Glyco-Enzyme Repository database <http://glycoenzymes.ccr.c.uga.edu>. To determine whether the glycomic subfamilies of enzymes were statistically differentially expressed in OA versus RA cell populations, the Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test was used, considering statistically significant differences with a P-value 0.05 or less, as previously described [37].

3.4 | Cloning of Lentiviral-System-Based Construct for Modulating TMEM230 Protein Expression Level

The shTMEM230 sequence (for downregulation of endogenous TMEM230) was cloned into pcDNATM6.2-GW/EmGFP using the BLOCK-iTTM Pol II miR RNAi Expression Vector Kit with EmGFP (K493600, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions and as previously described [37]. Lentivirus particles were produced in HEK293T cells by transfecting pCDH or pLENTI vectors together with psPAX2 and pMD2.G (gift from Didier Trono, Addgene plasmids #12260 and #12259) as helper vectors for 2nd-generation viral packaging (with a ratio 4:3:1, respectively) using the LipofectamineTM 2000 Transfection Reagent (11668027, Thermo Fisher Scientific Waltham, MA, USA) following manufacturer's instructions and as previously described [37].

3.5 | Adherent Cell Cultures

The human brain glioblastoma U87-MG cell line was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) and maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, Euroclone, ECB7501L) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Sigma, F7524), 1% glutamine (Cambrex, BE17-605E) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (P/S, Life Technology, 15140-122). Cells were cultured to 80% level of confluence in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37°C. Transduction was performed on adherent U87 cells at concentration of 10,000 cells/cm² using empty green fluorescent protein (GFP), TMEM230-GFP (for TMEM230 upregulation), and shTMEM230-GFP (for downregulation) lentiviral vectors, respectively. The efficiency of transduction was verified by microscope observation. Cells were allowed to recover for two passages in adherent culture and used for immunofluorescence analysis and other assays.

3.6 | Microchannel Formation and Nuclei Staining

20,000 U87-MG glioblastoma cells were plated on top of growth factor reduced Matrigel (BD Biosciences, 35623) bed in 48-well

plates (Greiner, Twin-Helix, 677180) for microchannel assay. U87-MG cells were grown in standard glial growth medium and monitored over time for 48 h as previously described [37]. U87 cell cultured on 48-well plates of Matrigel were stained with 4',6'-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI, Sigma, D9542) after 48 h. The DAPI solution (100 μ l) was directly added to Matrigel cultures, incubated for 5 min at room temperature and observed immediately with fluorescence microscope.

3.7 | Immunofluorescence Analysis

U87 control, and cells in which TMEM230 expression were modulated using the lentiviral approach (TMEM230mRNA and shTMEM230 cells) were fixed with 4% Paraformaldehyde (Sigma) in 1 \times PBS for 10 min at room temperature (RT). Cells were incubated with a blocking buffer of 5% normal goat serum in 1 \times PBS. The primary antibodies used were anti-phalloidin-TRITC conjugated (1:2000, Sigma, P1951) or anti-C20ORF30 (TMEM230, 1:1000, Santa Cruz, sc-85410) all incubated for 2 h at RT. The cells were washed with 1 \times PBS and incubated with a secondary antibody of goat anti-rabbit Alexafluor-555 (1:500 dilution, A21429, Life Technologies) for 1 h at RT. Nuclei were visualized with bisbenzimidazole Hoechst 33342 (Sigma, B2261) staining.

3.8 | Super-Resolution Microscopy

Super-resolution imaging data were collected by using a Stellaris 8 Falcon τ -STED microscope (Leica Microsystems, Mannheim, Germany) equipped with a supercontinuum pulsed (80 MHz) white light laser (WLL), a 775 nm donut-shaped STED (stimulated emission depletion) laser and an HC PL APO CS2 100 \times /1.40 oil immersion objective lens. The software LAS X (v4.5) was used for collecting images. Alexafluor594 was excited with both the WLL at 590 nm and the STED laser; its emission was collected in the range of 600–700 nm. The Hoechst, used for staining the nucleus, was excited at 440 nm, and its emission was collected in the range of 448–520 nm. For both fluorophores, we used hybrid detectors (Leica Microsystems) in counting mode with a pixel dwell-time of 0.72 μ s and 6-line accumulation.

4 | Results

4.1 | Dysregulated Glycosylation Enzymes in Autoimmunity

To understand the basis of autoimmunity or cancer as diseases of altered glycan expression requires characterizing the expression of glycan and glycoconjugate processing enzymes, as glycan profiles are not determinable using high-throughput RNA sequencing. Glycoconjugate profiles can only be indirectly inferred by determining which enzymes that generate, process and modify glycans are expressed. We previously investigated proteins that are glycoconjugated using published single cell sequencing datasets from RA and OA patient derived synovial tissue [9]. In this study, we extend our study to investigate

enzymes that generate, process and modify glycan associated synthesis and processing enzyme genes.

4.2 | Single Cell RNA Sequencing Data Analysis

Single cell RNA sequencing data from publicly available datasets of synovial tissue were acquired from Gene Expression Omnibus repository: (GSE152805) for OA and (GSE200815) for RA patients [9]. Single cell transcriptomic analysis was performed with 4 RA and 3 OA datasets (Chromium 10X Genomics). Integration of the OA and RA datasets was performed to allow combination of the different cell clusters of synovial tissue to be compared between RA and OA. Essentially, corresponding filtered feature barcode matrix files were imported in R (4.1.0) and analyzed by the Seurat package (V.4.0.6) as previously described [37]. The different clusters of patient cells were defined by specific markers from the literature, shown in Figure 1 and Table 1: (SF) synovial fibroblast 1, (Endo1) endothelial, (POSTN_SF) synovial fibroblast defined by POSTN gene, PRG4_SF (synovial fibroblast defined by PRG4 gene), IS_B-T-NK (immune system B, T, Natural Killer cells), (CXCL12_SF) synovial fibroblast defined by CXCL12 gene, (MP) macrophages, (SM) smooth muscle (predominantly from blood vessels), (DC) dendritic cells (macrophage like), (Endo2) endothelial cells (blood vessel), (SF2) synovial fibroblast 2, (PDC) plasmacytoid dendritic cells, (Endo3) endothelial cells (blood vessels), and (IS_O) immune system cells “Others” [70].

4.3 | Glycosyl Transferases, Glycosyl Hydrolases and Glycan Modifying Enzymes

To identify regulatory enzymatic genes involved in autoimmunity, cell clusters were analyzed by expression of glycan processing enzyme encoding genes. The expression profiles of the glycomic enzymes were evaluated in RA versus OA specific cell clusters obtained by single cell RNA sequencing analysis. Glycomic gene sets were created using the classification of the Glyco-Enzyme Repository (<http://glycoenzymes.ccruc.uga.edu>) from the Carbohydrate-Active Enzymes (CAZymes) CAZy database (<http://www.cazy.org>). Wilcoxon Rank-Sum method and Presto R Package (<https://github.com/immunogenomics/presto>) were used to identify differentially expressed genes (DEG) [9]. A \log_2 FC p value ≤ 0.05 was used for average expression of genes in a cluster, relative to the average expression in all other clusters combined. The different cell clusters from RA and OA were analyzed by performing 15 comparisons (14 by comparing the different cell clusters one to each other and 1 by comparing all cell clusters together (bulk)). A total of 363 Human Glycosylation Enzyme encoding genes were collected from the Glyco-Enzyme Repository database <http://glycoenzymes.ccruc.uga.edu>.

Out of the 363 glycoenzyme genes reported in the CAZy database, 212 were organized in 26 subfamilies of Glycosyl Transferases (GTs) (representative images shown in Figures 2, 3); 79 were organized in 43 subfamilies of Glycoside Hydrolases (GHs) (representative Figures 4, 5); 35 genes were part of the Sulfotransferases (SulfoTs) family; 37 genes were part of the family of “other” glycan genes.

FIGURE 1 | Osteoarthritis (OA) and rheumatoid arthritis (RA) synovial tissue transcriptomic map clustered by cell type. OA and RA high-resolution visualization of synovial tissue composition obtained by Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) plot of synovial tissue cell types after integrating 3 OA (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE152805>) and 4 RA (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE200815>) datasets. Clusters were identified according to the expression of representative specific markers according to Table 1 and Abeni et al, 2024.

The GTs, GHs, STs and the “Other” glycan genes were localized in the 14 RA and OA synovial tissue clusters and the expression level of each enzyme in each RA/OA cluster was compared. To determine whether the glycomic sub-families of enzymes were statistically differentially expressed in RA versus OA cell populations, the Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test was used [9]. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

4.4 | Glycosyl Transferase Family Expression in RA

Analysis showed that 8 out of 26 subfamilies analyzed from the GT family, GT2, GT8, GT13, GT21, GT29, GT31, GT39, and GT41 were differentially expressed in different cell clusters of the RA and OA diseases (Table 2). Four subfamilies, GT21, GT29, GT39, GT41 were exclusively and significantly expressed in RA clusters: the GT21 subfamily was expressed in: SF1 (P value 0.029), Endo1 (P value 0.011), PRG4_SF (P value 0.043), CXCL12_SF (P value 0.024), SM (P value 0.037) and Endo 2 (P value 0.019); the GT29 and GT39 subfamilies were both expressed in the IS-B-T-NK cell clusters (P value 0.024 and 0.042 respectively); the GT 41 subfamily was expressed in the IS-B-T-NK cluster with P value 0.022, and in the CXCL12_SF, and SM clusters, both with P value 0.046.

4.5 | Glycosyl Transferases Family Expression in OA

Four subfamilies of GTs: GT2, GT8, GT13 and GT31 were exclusively and significantly expressed in the OA clusters GT2 in

POSTN_SF (P value 0.02) and MP clusters (P value 0.05); GT8 in PRG4_SF (P value 0.03); GT13 in SF-1 and DC clusters (P value 0.036 and 0.034 respectively); GT31 in POSTN_SF cluster (P value 0.05) (Table 2).

4.6 | Glycosyl Hydrolase Family Expression in RA

Three out of the 43 families of Glycosyl Hydrolases: GH13, GH20, GH22 were differentially expressed in different RA and OA clusters (Table 2). The GH subfamilies GH13 and GH22 were exclusively expressed in RA clusters. GH13 in the SF1 and DC clusters (P value 0.036 and 0.03 respectively). GH22 in the MP (P value 0.0058) and DC clusters (P value 0.043).

4.7 | Glycosyl Hydrolase Family Expression in OA

GH20 subfamily was exclusively significantly expressed in the OA clusters Endo1 (P value 0.024) and DC (P value 0.01) (Table 2).

4.8 | Sulfotransferase Family Expression in RA

The family of SulfoT comprising the 35 enzymes was exclusively and significantly expressed in 4 RA clusters: in SF1 (P value 0.0095), in CXCL12_SF (P value 0.036), in MP (P value 0.034) and in DC (P value 0.022) (Table 2). No SulfoT enzymes were detected with significant expression in OA.

TABLE 1 | Cell markers used for defining the unique patient cell clusters in RA and OA in single cell sequencing analysis.

1. **PRG4 SF (synovial lining fibroblast) defining markers:** MMP3, PRG4, HBEGF, DEFB1, TWISTNB, ERFFI1, ITGB8, TIMP3, CLIC5, HTRA1, TPR, SPARCL1, CRTAC1, SEMA3C, SEMA5A, NTN4, FN1, ITGBL1, MT1G, GPR1.
2. **CXCL12 SF (synovial sub-lining fibroblast) markers:** CXCL12, CHI3L2, APOE, COL14A1, IGFBP4, EFEMP1, LAMB1, CP, PTGDS, JUN, EGR1, ZFP36, CCL2, ID3, GAS1, SOCS3, CHI3L1, SFRP1, AHR, ADAMTS1.
3. **POSTN SF (synovial fibroblast) markers:** POSTN, COL1A1, COL3A1, SPARC, COL1A2, LGALS1, COL5A2, AEBP1, ADAM12, OGN, COL5A1, ASPN, DPT, THBS2, TGFBI, IGFBP3, CTHRC1, THBS1, TNC, SERPINE1.
4. **CXCL14 SF (synovial fibroblast) markers:** CXCL14, MFAP5, FBLN2, IGF1, FBLN1, C3, AKAP12, DCN, VCAN, ASPN, GSN, THY1, CPE, SFRP2, FBN1, IGFBP6, PI16, HTRA3, APOD.
5. **Macrophage cell markers:** C1QA, C1QB, C1QC, FTL, MARCO, LGMN, PLTP, FOLR2, CFD, CTSB, CD163, CTSL, GPNMB, CTSZ, CD68, APOC1, APOE, CCL18, SELENOP, SPP1.
6. **Dendritic cell markers:** FCN1, LGALS2, S100A12, LYZ, FCER1A, SERPINA1, CSTA, EREG, MNDA, VCAN, CLEC10A, LST1, THBS1, G0S2, PPIF, NAMPT, IL1B, C15orf48, S100A8, S100A9.
7. **PDC plasmacytoid dendritic cell markers:** KRT5, GZMB, PLD4, SPIB, JCHAIN, TSPAN13, PTPRS, IRF4, PLAC8, ITM2C, IL3RA, C12orf75, PTGDS, AL807752.7, TCF4, SOX4, CCDC50, PPP1R14B, IRF8, IRF7.
8. **T cell markers:** TRAC, LTB, CD2, SPOCK2, TRBC2, IL7R, CD3D, IL32, ETS1, CD3G, KLRB1, CD3E, BCL11B, SYNE2, CD52, RORA, CTLA4, TNFAIP3, TCF7, CXCL13.
9. **B cell markers:** MS4A1, CD79A, CD19, BANK1, IGHD, LINC00926, CD22, RALGPS2, CD79B, LY9, CCR7, ADAM28, CD37, HVCN1, LTB, SELL, POU2F2, BIRC3, SMIM14, CD69.
10. **Natural Killer cell (IS NK) markers:** CCL5, NKG7, GZMA, CST7, CTSW, GZMK, GZMH, CD8A, GZMM, GZMB, PRF1, KLRD1, IL32, CD3D, DUSP2, RUNX3, GNLY, TUBA4A, PIK3R1, CCL4.
11. **Plasma cell markers:** MZB1, DERL3, FKBP11, IGHG2, JCHAIN, IGHG4, IGHG1, IGHG3, IGHGP, IGKV4-1, XBP1, SSR4, WT1-AS, IGLC3, IGHM, IGLC2, IGKC, IGHA1.
12. **Mast cell markers:** CPA3, TPSAB1, MS4A2, TPSB2, HDC, KIT, CTSG, SLC18A2, ADCYAP1, GATA2, HPGD, COL6A3, MTRNR2L2, TUBA1A, COL1A1, COL1A2, CD69, COL3A1, BGN.

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

-
13. **Endothelial cell markers:** TM4SF1, AQP1, RAMP2, VWF, PLVAP, CLEC14A, ACKR1, CLDN5, CAV1, SPARCL1, HSPG2, GNG11, ADIRF, IGFBP7, ID1, POSTN, MGP, IFITM3, FABP4, CXCL10.
 14. **Smooth muscle cell markers:** RGS5, ACTA2, SOD3, RERGL, TPM2, MYH11, NDUFA4L2, MYL9, C11orf96, COL18A1, TAGLN, CALD1, ADIRF, SPARCL1, IGFBP7, TPM1, MGP, TIMP3, DSTN, CCL2.
-

4.9 | “Other” Glycan Family Expression in RA

The “other” glycan enzyme genes (comprising 26 members) were significantly differentially expressed in 3 RA clusters: in SF1 (P value 0.0037); in POSTN_SF (P value 0.0095); in IS_B-T-NK cell cluster (P value 0.0091) (Table 2).

4.10 | The “Other” Glycan Family Expression in OA

The “other” glycan enzyme genes were significantly differentially expressed in 2 OA clusters: in SM (P value 0.025) and in Endo2 cluster with P value 0.043 (Table 2).

In summary results show that 8 out of the 26 subfamilies of Glycosyl Transferase enzymes analyzed (GT2, 8, 13, 21, 29 31 39, and 41) and 3 out of the 43 subfamilies of Glycoside Hydrolases (GH13, GH20, GH22) were expressed in different RA/OA clusters with a P value 0.05 or less (Table 2). A total of 13 RA clusters express Glycosyl Transferase enzymes, while only 6 OA clusters express GT enzymes. Cell types that are prominent in disease progression are Dendritic Cells and Macrophages, phagocytic cells in which secretion of metalloproteins is regulated by TMEM230. Dendritic Cell cluster shows 5 subfamilies of glycomic processing enzymes, B-T and Natural Killer cell clusters show 4 subfamilies, while Macrophages, Smooth Muscle and SF1 clusters show expression of 3 subfamilies of glycomic enzymes in OA or RA.

The GT subfamilies GT21, GT29, GT39, and GT41, the GH subfamily GH13 and GH22, the ST family, and the “Other” family of Glycan processing enzymes are exclusively expressed in RA clusters. The GT2, GT8, GT13 GT31 and the GH20 subfamilies are exclusively expressed in OA clusters. The GT21 is the only one subfamily expressed in 6 different RA clusters.

4.11 | Regulation of Glycan Synthesis, Processing and Modifying Enzymes in Blood Vessel, Synovial Fibroblast and Immune System Cells in Rheumatoid Arthritis by TMEM230

Our previous studies support that TMEM230 regulates various functions of the ES of diverse cell types, including the ER and lysosomes as indicated by the modulation of lysosome enzyme RNASET2 expression (Figure 6). In support that TMEM230 may have a role in autoimmunity, TMEM230

FIGURE 2 | Representative expression profile of glycosyl transferase subfamily, GT29, in different OA and RA cell clusters, showing upregulation in some RA clusters. Left Panel. Localization of GT29, enzyme on the UMAP plot of the OA and RA synovial tissue cell clusters. Colors indicate the levels of expression from 1 (gray) to 3 (blue), low to high. Right Panel. Box plot graphical visualization of the expression profile of the GT29, sub-family in RA and OA cell clusters. The y axis represents the expression level. p value < 0.05 was calculated by Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test.

FIGURE 3 | Representative expression profile of glycosyl transferase subfamily, GT32, in different OA and RA cell clusters, showing upregulation in some OA clusters. Left Panel. Localization of GT32, enzyme on the UMAP plot of the OA and RA synovial tissue cell clusters. Colors indicate the levels of expression from 1 (gray) to 3 (blue), low to high. Right Panel. Box plot graphical visualization of the expression profile of the GT32, sub-family in RA and OA cell clusters. The y axis represents the expression level. p value < 0.05 was calculated by Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test.

was detected as downregulated in all synovial tissue cell types from patients with RA compared to OA by single cell transcriptomic analysis (Figures 7, 8). Downregulation of TMEM230 was prominent in all blood vessel endothelial cells (Endo 1, 2, and 3) and smooth muscle (SM) cells that surround the ECs. We previously characterized the role of TMEM230 in blood vessels as being necessary to form

functional blood vessels. When aberrantly overexpressed TMEM230 promoted aggressive growth of blood vessels that were “leaky” due to loss of normal endothelial and smooth muscle cell interactions and contacts [2, 9, 37]. These types of aberrant blood vessel features were associated with intravasation and extravasation of immune cells as we previously demonstrated [2, 9, 37]. How downregulation of

FIGURE 4 | Representative expression profile of glycosyl hydrolase subfamily, GH20. in different OA and RA cell clusters, showing upregulation in OA clusters. Left Panel. Localization of GH20. enzyme on the UMAP plot of the OA and RA synovial tissue cell clusters. Colors indicate the levels of expression from 1 (gray) to 3 (blue), low to high. Right Panel. Box plot graphical visualization of the expression profile of the GH20. sub-family in RA and OA cell clusters. The y axis represents the expression level. p value < 0.05 was calculated by Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test.

FIGURE 5 | Representative expression profile of glycosyl hydrolase subfamily, GH2. in different OA and RA cell clusters, showing upregulation in OA clusters. Left Panel. Localization of GH2. enzyme on the UMAP plot of the OA and RA synovial tissue cell clusters. Colors indicate the levels of expression from 1 (gray) to 3 (blue), low to high. Right Panel. Box plot graphical visualization of the expression profile of the GH2. sub-family in RA and OA cell clusters. The y axis represents the expression level. p value < 0.05 was calculated by Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test.

TMEM230 in ECs may contribute to the pathophysiology of RA cannot be determined in this study from the sequencing analysis. TMEM230 expression is required for normal blood vessel structure whereas aberrantly high levels of TMEM230 promote hypervascularization of nonfunctional “leaky” blood vessels. It may be likely that the pathophysiological effect of loss of TMEM230 expression may be on the immune system of RA patients. For instance, altered leukocyte functions, such as homing, movement, and intravasation and extravasation capacity of immune cells into blood vessels was supported by loss of detectable levels of TMEM230 expression in immune system T, B and Natural Killer cells (IS_BTnk, Figure 8). TMEM230 was also downregulated in all synovial fibroblast cells (PRG4_SF, POSTN_SF, SF1, SF2,

and CXCL12_SF, Figure 8). We previously demonstrated that specific levels of TMEM230 expression determine movement and phagocytic activity of macrophage, fibroblast and glial cells (Figure 9) [2, 9, 37]. Sustained down-regulation of TMEM230 expression promoted chronic destructive tissue remodeling or lack of normal tissue remodeling capacity of these types of phagocytic cells [2, 9, 37]. To evaluate whether TMEM230 expression may modulate different glycan profiles in endothelial, smooth muscle, fibroblast cells and immune cells we investigated the expression profiles of glycosylation enzymes (Table 2). In agreement that TMEM230 may regulate phagocytic activities of synovial cells, blood vessel cells, and immune system cells, glycosylation enzymes expression was significantly more modulated in RA compared to OA patient samples (Table 2).

TABLE 2 | Families of glycomic enzymes expressed in OA or RA clusters of different cell types. Listed are the subfamilies of the glycomic enzyme genes belonging to the larger family Glycosyl Transferases (column GT), Glycosyl Hydrolase (column GH), Sulfo Transferase (column ST) and “Other” Glycan enzymes (column “other”) that are differentially expressed with a mRNA fold change P value ≤ 0.05. Subfamilies were created using the classification of the Glyco-Enzyme Repository (<http://glycoenzymes.ccr.c.uga.edu>) from the Carbohydrate-Active Enzymes (CAZymes) CAZy database.

	Glycosyl Transferases										Glycosyl Hydrolases					Sulfo Transferases	Other Glycan Processing Enzymes
	GT2	GT8	GT13	GT21	GT29	GT31	GT39	GT41	GH13	GH20	GH22						
Osteoarthritis																	
Rheumatoid Arthritis																	
SF_1			0.036	0.029						0.036					0.0095		0.0037
Endo1				0.011													
POPSTN_SF	0.02				0.05												0.0095
PRG4_SF		0.03		0.043													
IS_BTKN					0.024				0.022								0.0091
CXCL12_SF				0.024					0.046								
MP	0.05													0.0058			
SM				0.037					0.046								0.025
DC			0.034														
Endo2				0.019										0.043			0.043
SF2																	
PDC																	
Endo3																	
IS_O																	

FIGURE 6 | Immunofluorescence analysis of RNASET2 expression in U87-MG control and TMEM230 mRNA + GFP transduced cells. Nuclei are visualized with DAPI. Staining supports that TMEM230 regulates the expression of RNASET2, a tumor and immune associated RNase regulating RNA digestion and turnover in lysosomes and extracellular matrix. Expression of RNASET2 was upregulated in cells in which TMEM230 mRNA expression was upregulated.

FIGURE 7 | Expression profile of TMEM230 and RNASET2 in OA and RA cell clusters, with cell clusters defined by markers from Table 1. Localization of TMEM230 and RNASET2 on the UMAP plot of the OA and RA synovial tissue cell clusters. Colors indicate the levels of expression from 1 (gray) to 3 (blue), low to high.

FIGURE 8 | Box plot graphical visualization of the expression profile of the TMEM230 in OA and RA. The y axis represents the expression level. p value < 0.05 was calculated by Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test. TMEM230 expression is downregulated in all cell types from RA patients compared to OA. TMEM230 expression is very low or not detected in RA patient Immune System cells (see DC, PDC and B, T and Natural Killer cells) compared to OA, suggesting that loss of TMEM230 promotes autoimmune features associated in with RA.

FIGURE 9 | TMEM230 promotes aberrant remodeling of the extracellular microenvironment by excessive microchannel formation and infiltration of U87-MG glial cells by inducing secretion of metalloproteinases and scaffolds (glycoproteins and proteoglycans) that enhance cell traction and migration. Red arrows: microchannels in which glial cells are migrating; black arrows: glial cells infiltrating into 3D Matrigel. Blue is DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) fluorescent staining of glial cell nuclei. While loss of TMEM230 may promote autoimmune features associated with RA (Figure 8), overexpression of TMEM230 induces infiltrating aggressive tumor features in U87-MG glioblastoma cells.

These changes may be associated with altered behavior of various cell types associated with intravasation and extravasation, or extracellular tissue remodeling through the modulation of ER dependent glycosylation or regulation of glycoconjugated protein turnover through lysosome enzymes such as RNASET2 (Figure 10).

4.12 | TMEM230 Regulation of Proteins That Are Glycoconjugated in GBM Patients

Our previous expression analyses of published and open access mRNA sequencing datasets determined that TMEM230 was differentially expressed in tumor tissue cells from patients with low- or high- grade gliomas [1, 2, 37]. Tumor patient gene expression analyses supported that TMEM230 has prognostic value as a tumor marker for aggressive high-grade gliomas since a higher level of TMEM230 was associated with lower patient survivability. Higher TMEM230 was also associated with worse prognosis. Moreover, it was observed that a higher percentage of patients died more rapidly compared to patients with lower expression of TMEM230. The aggressive tumor features in GBM were demonstrated to be induced by the ability of TMEM230 to promote destructive tissue remodeling and angiogenesis, and micro channeling into 3D extracellular matrix. We therefore investigated whether the aggressive tumor properties associated with high levels of TMEM230 in GBM patients may be associated with different glycoconjugate profiles. To identify specific genes, cellular components and pathways differentially expressed with TMEM230, transcriptomic analysis of approximately 200 patient samples with low grade gliomas (LGG) and a cohort of 172 patient samples with GBM from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) RNA sequencing (RNAseq) database were carried out (The Cancer Genome Atlas Research Network). Analyses was performed using the TCGA2STAT R Package as previously described [1, 2, 37]. Transcriptomic analyses of oligodendroglioma and GBM patient tumor tissues were performed by correlating gene expressions in GBM and LGG patients with high or low TMEM230 expression (Supplementary Table 1). In agreement that TMEM230 is a transmembrane protein of the ER, higher levels of TMEM230 in tumor samples from GBM compared to LGG patients were associated with increased expression of ER genes, supporting that increased ER activity is correlated with aggressive tumor features of GBM (Supplementary Table 1). TMEM230 was also previously found by our group to be associated with cell infiltration and microchannel formation when upregulated in U87-MG, a human cell line with cancer properties that recapitulates aggressive features of tumor cells from patients with glioblastoma multiforme (Figure 9) and in tumor associated macrophage cells (not shown). Downregulation of TMEM230 in U87-MG cells resulted in loss of destructive tissue remodeling and vascular mimicry behavior, previously shown [1, 2, 37]. Elevated levels of TMEM230 associated with destructive remodeling of the tumor extracellular microenvironment were due to TMEM230 induced secretion of metalloproteinases and scar forming scaffolds (glycoproteins and proteoglycans) that enhance cell traction and migration [1, 2, 37]. DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) fluorescent staining of nuclei showed that 3-dimensional lumen formation (Figure 9, red arrows) and migration of tumor glial cells (black arrows) are promoted by secretion or phagocytosis of extracellular scaffolds rather than by cell-to-cell contacts such as it occurs in blood vessels, supporting that TMEM230 also regulates phagocytosis.

Early evolutionary function of glycans in metazoans was in cell-to-cell and cell-to-extracellular environment recognition and adhesion of glycoconjugates [11]. Loss of normal cell-to-cell and cell-to-extracellular environment recognition and adhesion of

FIGURE 10 | Box plot graphical visualization of the expression profile of the RNASET2 (left panel, showing cell clusters with highest expression of RNASET2) and RA or OA comparative cluster analysis (right panel). The y axis represents the expression level. p value < 0.05 was calculated by Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) test.

glycoconjugates are hallmarks in cancer development [71]. As most secreted factors are glycoconjugates and extracellular scaffolds, and key signaling components of the plasma membrane are also glycoconjugates, we investigated in this study whether different levels of TMEM230 expression were associated with change in microfilament structural arrangements. Glycoconjugate functions in cell-to-cell and cell-to-extracellular environment recognition and adhesion are dependent on their trafficking onto the plasma membrane of cells and their secretion. Recognition and adhesion are dynamic processes dependent on the internalization of glycoconjugates contained in endosomes, exosomes, and vesicles on intracellular scaffolds such as microfilament actin (stained with fluorescein isothiocyanate-phalloidin, Figure 11) [9]. Increased trafficking of glycoconjugate and glycan cargo to the plasma membrane of cells for secretion (exosomes) was indicated by increased expression of genes that support actin cytoskeleton scaffold synthesis and homeostasis in GBM (Figure 11, Supplementary Table 1). Phalloidin was used to investigate the distribution of F-actin in U87-MG in which TMEM230 expression levels were modulated. Phalloidin prevents ATP induced depolymerization of F-actin fibers and specifically interacts at the interface between F-actin subunits. Native (Figure 11, Panel A) or increased (Panel B) expression of TMEM230 recapitulates morphologically actin-based growth cone motility and guidance as commonly associated with nerve growth cones, where actin is extended by ATP dependent polymerization into longer “filamentous” threads (see white arrows). By comparing U87-MG cells with different expression levels of TMEM230 (Figure 11) we determined that cells with lower levels of TMEM230 (for instance native levels panel A, or cells in which the endogenous levels of TMEM230 were downregulated with short hairpins against TMEM230 mRNA, Panel C) appear with a more

“globular” morphology associated with monomer units of actin. Active and dynamic actin networks that undergo rearrangements are involved in several processes including cell metabolism and cell movement, phagocytosis, exosome movement and secretion, and immune system leukocyte cell movement. Our research also supports that TMEM230 may regulate cell and tissue remodeling through proteoglycans synthesis or secretion and that expression of syndecans were modulated by constitutive downregulation of TMEM230 in U87-MG cells [37]. Syndecans are proteoglycan regulators of cell-surface microdomains that act as co-receptors which allow for interaction with many different types extracellular (ECM) ligands including fibronectin (*FNI*) [19, 72–75]. Syndecans and fibronectin expressions were both found altered with changes in TMEM230 expression (Supplementary Table 1 and Supplementary Figure 1). Fibronectin promotes normal or disease associated wound healing by inducing the formation of a functional substratum for migration and growth of cells.

The ER is an organelle that initiates the earliest steps of glycan synthesis and glycosylation for ES dependent glycoconjugate sorting, trafficking, and secretion. Evidence that TMEM230 may modulate ER activity was indicated by change in expression of key ER associated genes correlated with different levels of TMEM230 in GBM patients (Supplementary Table 1). As the ER is also known to be essential for linking the innate and adaptive immune systems by regulating intracellular trafficking in antigen presentation and antibody formation we investigated whether TMEM230 regulates, and links innate and adaptive immune system components [76, 77]. Sequencing analysis supported that increased expression of TMEM230 was predominantly associated with increased expression of glycoproteins and proteoglycans in GBM patients compared to patients

FIGURE 11 | Legend on next page.

with LGG (Supplementary Table 1). As TMEM230 is an ER protein, not surprisingly increase in glycoconjugated protein expression was associated primarily with N-linked (GlcNAc) glycosylation (Supplementary Table 1). TMEM230 expression was also linked predominantly with increase in ER lumen gene and plasma membrane gene trafficking. N-linked glycosylation and plasma membrane glycoproteins are associated with the ER. O-linked (Gal) glycosylation was limited to a few genes, namely C1QB, COL1A1, C1QA, COL3A1, COL14A1, COL6A3, C1QC. A Benjamini score of 4,17E-78 indicated that N-linked glycosylation was the primary cellular activity regulated by TMEM230 in cancer, with over 1000 genes associated with upregulation of TMEM230 being glycoproteins (Benjamini score 3.64E-91). Of these, heparin binding, IgG binding, proteoglycans in cancer were upregulated with upregulation of TMEM230 in GBM. For instance, heparanase (HPSE), an enzyme that acts both at the cell-surface and within the extracellular matrix to degrade polymeric heparin sulfate into shorter chain length oligosaccharides was upregulated suggesting that the destructive tissue remodeling observed in U87-MG cells with upregulation of TMEM230 may in part be due to the activity of secreted HSPE. Evidence that TMEM230 in GBM may regulate immune cells was observed with genes of Natural Killer cells, Mast cells, B cells and leukocyte properties (migration) also being upregulated with TMEM230 (Supplementary Table 1). Genes associated with innate and adaptive immunity and inflammation were also observed upregulated, as were MHC class I and II and antigen processing genes and T cell activation and stimulating effector genes. Our sequencing data therefore support that TMEM230 in cancer may regulate both the inherent and adaptive immune system pathways through various processes including professional APC and complement cascade processes (Supplementary Table 1). Antigens bind the major histocompatibility complex class II (MHC class II) heterodimers of dendritic cells, macrophages, B cells and certain types of endothelial cells. In the MHCII system for mounting an immune response, antigens to be presented are derived from extracellular proteins (not cytosolic). Loading of a MHC class II molecules occurs by phagocytosis where extracellular proteins are endocytosed, digested in the lysosomes and the resulting “processed” epitope are loaded onto MHC class II molecules before their migration to the cell surface [78]. In humans, the MHC class II protein complex is encoded by the human leukocyte antigen gene complex (HLA) that include HLA-P, HLA-DM, HLA-DOA, HLA-DOB, HLA-DQ and HLA-DR [79–82]. The innate immune system also induces the adaptive immune activities, such as the complement system (also called the complement cascade) activated by antibodies [27]. The complement system, as a part of innate immune humoral system “complements” the capacity of antibodies and phagocytes to remove pathogens and damaged cells from an organism, induces Inflammation, and destroys the cell

membranes of pathogens. In addition to being professional phagocytes, macrophages and dendritic cells activate the adaptive immunity system through interactions with T cells. Macrophages and dendritic cells stimulate CD8⁺ T cells through cross presentation of antigens peptides on MHC class I molecules and are professional antigen presenting cells (APCs) that can present phagocytosed antigens on major histocompatibility complex (MHC) II molecules on their cell surface for T helper cells [53]. Through this capacity, macrophage and dendritic cells can contribute to tumor cell proliferation and invasion by promoting inflammation factor induced tumor angiogenesis and suppressing antitumor immune cells. As the ER regulates protein stress response, not surprisingly we also identified genes associated to amyloidosis (Supplementary Table 1), supporting that the ER altered protein quality control and/or unfolded protein response may contribute to other types of endomembrane based disorders.

Collectively, our results support that TMEM230 contributes to tumor cell behavior through its role in regulating various N-linked generated glycoproteins (Figure 12, Supplementary Table 1). As a very large number of N-linked generated glycoproteins were found differently expressed dependent on the levels of TMEM230 in high- or low-grade gliomas. This supports that TMEM230 may represent a key target for therapeutic intervention in N-linked generated glycoproteins aggressive cancers. Many of the glycoconjugated HLA factors processed in the ER and identified with TMEM230 in GBM and RA were also associated with systemic lupus erythematosus (Supplementary Table 1, for instance HLA-DMA, HLA-DMB, HLA-DOA, HLA-DOB, HLA-DQA2, HLA-DQA1, HLADPA1, HLA-DPB and HLA-DPA). Therefore, likely many N-linked generated glycoproteins in cancer may also have a role in other autoimmune disorders, linking altered glycan profiles with both cancer and autoimmunity.

5 | Discussion

In this study we showed that increased TMEM230 expression was associated with increased expression of ER structural genes and ER associated activities in cancer, supporting our previous published studies that TMEM230 is an ER protein (Supplementary Table 1) [2, 9, 37]. The ER has many activities such as protein synthesis and folding, and generation and trafficking of glycoconjugates [4, 54, 55, 83–85]. The ER as an organelle that integrates endomembrane trafficking and signaling, senses and regulates stress response in inflammation, immunity and oncogenesis. Improperly folded proteins induce unfolded protein response (UPR) as a stress response in the ER. In our transcriptomic analysis, we show that enzymes regulating glycosylation or glycoconjugated factors are differentially

FIGURE 11 | Super-resolution imaging of phalloidin and Hoechst in U87-MG cells expressing native levels of TMEM230 (A, where the lentivirus expresses only GFP), TMEM230 upregulated (B), and TMEM230 downregulated (shTMEM230) (C). Images were collected by using a Stellaris 8 Falcon τ -STED microscope. The Hoechst dye used for staining the nucleus was excited at 440 nm, and its emission was collected in the range of 448–520 nm. Alexafluor594 detection indicates expression of phalloidin (590 nm and the STED laser, and emission was collected in the range of 600–700 nm). Antibody staining for phalloidin is performed as described in Cocola 2021. Phalloidin was used to investigate the distribution of F-actin in U87-MG. Increasing expression of TMEM230 recapitulates morphologically actin-based growth cone motility and guidance as commonly associated with nerve growth cones, where actin is extended by ATP dependent polymerization into longer “filamentous” threads (see white arrows).

N-linked glycoproteins Trafficking to Plasma Membrane in Immune System Cells or Secretion in Cancer Cells

FIGURE 12 | Scheme of biosynthesis pathway of *N*-linked glycoproteins. The synthesis of *N*-linked glycan starts in the endoplasmic reticulum, continues in the Golgi and ends at the plasma membrane, where the *N*-linked glycoproteins are either secreted or becomes embedded in the plasma membrane. TMEM230 upregulation was found to promote increase of expression of mitochondria, motor protein and plasma membrane and secreted genes. Over 1000 glycoprotein or proteoglycan genes overexpressed with TMEM230 upregulation were associated with *N* linked glycosylation. These genes include immune system plasma membrane associated glycoconjugates such as MHC I or II heterodimers (Supplementary Table 1), or secreted glycoconjugates or glycoconjugate modifying enzymes (heparin binding, syndecans 1, 2, and 4, and heparinase, HSPE Supplementary Table 1).

expressed with different levels of TMEM230 expression in RA and GBM (Table 2 and Supplementary Table 1). Of the many functions of glycans in cells, one is assisting in proper protein folding and stability. Loss of protein quality can potentially contribute to immune disorders and cancer, especially in loss of normal cell-to-cell, cell-to-substratum and cell-to-extracellular matrix recognition and interactions in parenchyma tissue. Normal cell-to-cell and cell-to-substratum recognition and interactions is also essential in immune cell interactions within tissue, blood vessels and extracellular matrix. The initial steps in glycan synthesis and glycosylation for generating glycoconjugates occurs in the ER [5, 86]. The altered glycan theory in autoimmunity proposes that individuals with autoimmunity have unique alterations in their glycosylation profile that favors a pro-inflammatory immune response and that the effector function of the immune response is mediated by cells and humoral components of the immune system [18]. In this study we identified that TMEM230 expression level determines the expression patterns of MHC class I and II cells in GBM (Supplementary Table 1) and glycan processing enzymes (Table 2). One interpretation of the altered glycan theory is that a pro-inflammatory response is mediated by changes in glycosylation in the immune system cells. Here we show that TMEM230 alters enzyme expression of glycosylation associated genes in MHC I cells, such as fibroblast and smooth muscle cells, suggesting the interaction of diverse tissue cell types in addition to immune system cells contributes to an aberrant immune response and inflammation in cancer and in complement and coagulation cascade (Supplementary Table 1). By regulating the complement cascade TMEM230 may act as a hub for controlling membrane attack (the classical complement pathway), phagocytosis by opsonizing antigens (the alternative complement pathway), and inflammation (lectin pathway) both in autoimmunity and cancer [27, 87] Modulation of TMEM230 expression promoted changes in expression of the MHC class II

genes (HLA-DRB5, HLA-C, HLA-A, HLA-DMA, HLA-DMB, HLA-DPB1, HLA-DRA, HLA-DOA, HLA-DOB, HLA-DQA2, HLA-DQA1, HLA-DQB2, HLA-DRB1, HLA-DPA1, HLA-DQB1) and MHC class I genes (HLA-H, HFE, HLA-B, HLA-C, HLA-A, HLA-F, MR1, B2M, HLA-G, HLA-E, HLA-DQB1). The rough ER is the location for synthesis of lysosomal digestive enzymes (RNASET2, Figure 6) and linkage of a mannose-6-phosphate to peptides destined for lysosome. Synthesis of secreted factors and vesicles are regulated either constitutively with no tags or in a regulatory manner involving clathrin-assembly (Supplementary Table 1). How TMEM230 regulates the immune system in autoimmunity and cancer remains unknown by us in detail, but possible mechanisms are described below. Our data in this study show that many stress glycoproteins and proteoglycans overlap with the immune system functions. Future study by our group will be guided by our observation that most prominent pathways upregulated by TMEM230 are associated with integral membrane glycoconjugates, vesicle trafficking and secretion and targets of *N*-linked glycosylation (Supplementary Table 1). Integral membrane glycoconjugates that remain in the membrane of the ER become part of vesicles that shuttle to the plasma and organelle (mitochondria) membranes. In previous studies, we showed that high levels of TMEM230 were associated with increased mitochondrial activities such as electron transport in oxidative phosphorylation and in upregulation of ATP synthesis that power motor protein trafficking of cargo on intracellular scaffolds [37]. Additionally, we also previously showed that increase of oxidative phosphorylation with TMEM230 increased expression was coupled with an increase in synthesis of metalloproteins and in stress response cellular processes such as cytochromes P450, a superfamily of enzymes containing heme as a cofactor that function as monooxygenases [9]. Cytochromes are the most important detoxifiers in xenobiotics and are commonly found in the liver and have a protective role in

preventing cancer development. Cytochromes in general are terminal oxidase enzymes in electron transfer chains, and like TMEM230 are primarily membrane-associated proteins found in endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria. Cytochrome P450s potentially metabolize thousands of endogenous and exogenous chemicals, suggesting that TMEM230 may have a very important central role in the metabolism of toxic compounds including drugs and products of endogenous metabolism, or potentially their synthesis. TMEM230 as a regulator of metabolism of toxic compounds or drugs has important implications promoting or inhibiting autoimmune disorders or cancer, where a toxic environment may have an input in increasing the risk factor in pathogenesis.

5.1 | TMEM230 Regulator of Endoplasmic Reticulum Cellular Processes Including Synthesis, Processing and Intracellular Trafficking and Secretion of Protein Glycoconjugates in Tissue and ECM Remodeling and Cell-To-Substrate Interactions and Cell Migration

Concurrent to our early studies of *tmem230* regulation of the glycoproteins *notch* ligand and receptors TMEM230 gene mutations in Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease human patients were identified, suggesting high risk of Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD) development. *TMEM230* as an ER component may have a role in the processing, folding, quality control, and trafficking of glycans and glycoconjugates such as proteins. Loss of expression or activity, or overexpression of TMEM230 was proposed for promoting aberrant glycan and protein stability and aggregation in PD and AD. Aberrant glycan and protein stability and aggregation may also lead to autoimmunity or cancer. We and others have characterized the functions of *NOTCH* ligands and receptors in normal and disease development in diverse tissues in zebrafish (angiogenesis) and human breast cancer and stem cell (SC) regulation. In early embryonic development and tumor formation, *NOTCH* mediates differentiation or wound healing of tissue Stem Cells (SCs) and cancer stem cells (CSCs). As an apparent master regulator of the *NOTCH* signaling pathway, we previously investigated whether *TMEM230* may modulate expression, intracellular trafficking, and secretion of glycoconjugated proteins in, blood vessels, and immune system cells in associated human disorders and cancer [38]. We demonstrated that TMEM230 aberrant expression is associated with giant cell arteritis (GCA) where immune system cell movement is a key feature of this human autoimmune-like disorder [1, 9, 37]. In fact, caveolins, integral components of plasma membrane containing caveolae involved in receptor-independent endocytosis and intracellular trafficking of factors both in cancer initiation and in autoimmunity, were detected as modulated by different levels of TMEM230 (Supplementary Table 1) [88, 89].

5.2 | TMEM230 Regulation of Glycoprotein and Proteoglycan Expression in Tissue Remodeling

As many factors that are secreted from cells are glycoconjugates we investigated in previous studies whether CD81, a glycoprotein

associated with secreted vesicles and syndecan 1 (*SDC1*) expression may be modulated by TMEM230 [37]. Indeed, decreased expression of these genes were observed with constitutive TMEM230 downregulation in U-87 MG cells. CD81 was not detected in tissue culture media from cells in which TMEM230 was downregulated [37], while higher expression of CD81 was detected in conditioned media of U87-MG cells with constitutive over-expression of TMEM230 in respect to conditioned media collected from control cells, supporting that TMEM230 regulates extracellular vesicle generation or secretion. That TMEM230 may regulate proteoglycan synthesis or secretion is also supported by the observation that syndecans and fibronectin expressions were both found altered with changes in TMEM230 expression (Supplementary Table 1 and Supplementary Figure 1). Fibronectin promotes normal or disease associated wound healing by inducing the formation of a functional substratum for cell migration and growth. Wound healing is a stepwise process in which development and organization of blood clots and granulation tissue as well as degradation and resynthesis of the connective tissue matrix scaffolds (such as glycoconjugates) occur.

Fibroblast, macrophage and glial cells with phagocytic activity promote tissue remodeling by forming cellular fibronectin. ECM remodeling involves both degradation by proteases and secretion of glycoconjugated protein scaffolds. We previously demonstrated that TMEM230 expression was necessary for expression or secretion of diverse proteases, including MMPs that digest plasma FN1 in cells with phagocytic activity. In agreement that TMEM230 may have a role in phagocytic cells expression or secretion of FN1, reduced FN1 detection was observed in U87-MG cells with lentiviral downregulation of TMEM230 with concomitant loss of cell migration and 3D Matrigel remodeling capacity. Our cell based in vitro assays agreed with our previously published sequencing analysis of patients with high-grade glioblastoma showing that that TMEM230 regulates both tissue digestion (matrix metalloproteinases, MMP) and wound healing (FN1). TMEM230 may also promote cancer by conferring resistance to apoptosis as we have previously investigated and as demonstrated for fibronectin expressing cancer cells. Another function of TMEM230 regulation of fibronectin may be in promoting induction of inflammatory lesions and changes in collagen deposition by FN1. We previously observed that with downregulation of FN1 induced by TMEM230 downregulation collagen fibril detection was also reduced [37]. Fibronectin interacts with diverse cell surface glycoproteins, such as CD44, a regulator of cell-cell and cell-to-substratum interactions. As for fibronectin, CD44 was demonstrated by our group to be downregulated in U87-MG cells by lentiviral induced downregulation of TMEM230. Like TMEM230, both fibronectin and CD44 have diverse functions including proliferation, differentiation, migration, homing and survival of cells in blood vessel and cancer induced tissue remodeling. CD44 is a receptor for hyaluronic acid and interacts with collagens and matrix metalloproteins (MMPs). CD44 also has a role in autoimmune disorders such as RA [19–21, 56, 57]. Regulation of glycan regulation by TMEM230 also has been supported by our previous study that shows that glycan containing polymers are important mediators of cancer cell mechano-transduction [10]. Stiffer tumors are characterized by increased glycan content on cancer cells and their associated extracellular matrix [90]. Also, glycans on glycoproteins may act

as barrier to protect against cancer cell secreting proteases. TMEM230 induced aberrant glycosylation may also influence vascular biology by controlling trafficking, migration, and signaling of endothelial cell receptors including vascular endothelial growth factor receptors, platelet EC adhesion molecules, NOTCH and integrins. We previously demonstrated that TMEM230 expression is modulated by hypoxic conditions and HIF-1 α expression (solid tumors grow < 2% O₂ tension) [2, 38]. We believe that pharmacological inhibitors of HIF-1 α and modulators of ER stress, although characterized by low specificity and anticancer efficacy when used as single agents, may be repurposed as chemosensitizers against hypoxic and chemo refractory tumors in the next future. In conclusion, our data supported that TMEM230 was essential for the expression or secretion of SDC1, FN1 and CD44, identifying a novel pathway of glycoproteins modulated by TMEM230. In previous studies we demonstrated that glycoproteins SDC1, FN1 and CD44 down-regulation was associated with loss of adhesion, migration, tissue remodeling and microchannel formation capacities of U87-MC cells. Our collective observations suggested that TMEM230 may represent a novel therapeutic approach for the development of new drugs that target glycoproteins.

5.3 | Candidate Molecular Roles of TMEM230 in ER Regulation of Glycoproteins and Proteoglycans in Cancer and Autoimmune Disorders

Glycosylation is essential in normal cell functions including in NOTCH signaling, a paradigm for cell fate specifications during metazoan development [41]. Both NOTCH and its ligands are diversely glycosylated by the addition of various glycan moieties. Glycosylation is necessary for inducing structural and functional changes, with disruption resulting in developmental disorders and disease, including cancer and RA [33, 38, 39, 91, 92]. tmem230 was originally identified as a master regulator of the Notch receptor and Notch ligands Delta and Serrate/Jagged signaling in angiogenesis in zebrafish by our group [38]. Precise modulation of tmem230 expression by itself was sufficient to rescue improper number of endothelial cells induced by aberrant expression or inhibition of the activity of genes associated with the NOTCH receptor and its ligands in zebrafish. Our previous studies also supported that overexpression of TMEM230 was associated with promoting growth of highly permeable and defective blood vessels and aggressive tissue remodeling of GBM. Restoration of TMEM230 expression level promoted blood vessel re-normalization and loss of tumor properties of human blood vessel endothelial cells derived from glial tumor cells in 3D culture assays in which TMEM230 expression was modulated by a lentiviral approach.

We have been investigating whether NOTCH signaling by TMEM230 has overlapping effects in ER dependent glycosylation in different normal and disease contributing tissue cell types, including in immune cell differentiation and homing, and in SC fate determination and CSC activity. TMEM230 may regulate disease processes in autoimmunity and cancer by regulating glycan synthesis, processing, conjugation and secretion as NOTCH and the NOTCH ligands Delta and Serrate/Jagged are all glycoproteins. Inactivation of glycosyltransferases

which initiate and elongate glycan remodeling of NOTCH were found to inhibit NOTCH signaling and normal angiogenesis. The extracellular domains of mammalian NOTCH proteins contain tandem epidermal growth factor-like (EGF) repeats most of which have O-linked glycan modifications. Our sequencing data presented in this study support that TMEM230 primarily modulates N-linked glycosylation (Supplementary Table 1). However, how TMEM230 functions in the NOTCH receptor and ligand signaling and NOTCH component interactions requires further investigation as many studies have indicated that O-GlcNAc (rather than N-linked) glycans were required for optimal hematopoiesis and T and B cell development for POFUT1 (Protein-O-FucosylTransferase 1) and O-Fucose Glycans to promote NOTCH signaling in lymphoid and myeloid differentiation and in RA. Although it was reported that the extracellular domain of NOTCH was also N-glycosylated.

5.4 | TMEM230 in Secretion of EVs Associated With Glycoconjugates in RA

Collectively our data support that TMEM230 expression was essential for the expression or secretion of specific glycoproteins (SDC1, FN1 and CD44) in U87-MG cells that have roles in cell adhesion, migration, tissue remodeling in wound healing. Intracellular activities and cellular and extracellular interactions of these proteins have been previously shown to modulate cancer and cancer associated fibroblast/endothelial/stromal cells reprogramming in promoting changes in tumor microenvironment/ECM that support tumorigenesis. Evidence suggests that remodeling was strongly supported by coordinated direct cell-to-cell-scaffold and glycan interactions. Reprogramming of tumor tissue cells also promotes ER synthesis and secretion of glycan associated factors containing vesicles [1, 7, 8, 23]. We previously showed using patient derived endothelial cells that TMEM230 promoted secretion of extracellular vehicles (EVs) marked by glycoprotein CD81. EVs secreted by cancer cells can suppress immune cell function induce fibroblasts and mesenchymal stem cells to acquire an inflammatory phenotype and enhanced phagocytic activities associated with microchannel and tissue remodeling in cancer and autoimmune disorders.

5.5 | TMEM230 Regulator of ER Dependent Glycan Modulation in Protein Folding and Quality Control

As an apparent regulator of the ER, TMEM230 may function in protein stress response (PSR) (Supplementary Table 1). ER stress is associated with accumulation of misfolded proteins in the ER lumen by the activation of unfolded protein response pathways [1, 4, 8, 15, 23, 43, 52, 53, 84, 93, 94]. If chronically activated, UPR promotes cell death via apoptosis and mitochondrial dysfunction. Alternatively, ER stress links inflammation to impaired insulin/metabolic signaling in the cancer and in inflammatory associated disorders. Our sequencing analysis presented in this study supports that aberrant modulation of TMEM230 expression may promote ER induced stress,

cell death, mitochondrial dysfunction in both cancer and RA (Supplementary Table 1).

5.6 | TMEM230 Regulator of Glycan Modulation of Immune Associated Cells in RA

The **synovial membrane**, a connective tissue that protects the inner surface of the capsule of synovial joints and bursa has direct interaction with the fibrous membrane on and synovial fluid [9, 25, 34, 36, 78, 95–101]. The synovial fluid at the tissue surface contains macrophage-like cells (MLC) and cells with fibroblast-like synoviocyte cells (FLS). The MCL cells maintain the synovial fluid and phagocytose debris from wear and injury. FLS cells produce hyaluronan and extracellular glycoaminoglycans in the synovial fluid. Changes between RA and OA in glycan synthesizing and processing enzymes were observed in both MLC and FLS cells (Supplementary Table 1). In early published studies it was observed that in rheumatic diseases a change in protein glycosylation was associated with inflammatory processes and disease progression. These changes included addition of glycans on (auto) antibodies, antigen-binding domains of receptors of immune associated cells, and changes in synovial fibroblast cells. These changes altered the glycan composition of the synovial tissue. Distinct N-glycosylation signatures in the fragment crystallizable (Fc) domain, characterized by fucosylation without sialylation or galactosylation were observed in autoantigen-specific IgG in patients. In this study we identified that altered expression of TMEM230 in RA appeared predominantly associated with N-linked glycosylation role. This is consistent with previous published observations that specific Fc and Fab IgG glycan signatures were associated with RA disease activity and remission. Autoantigen-specific IgGs, and autoreactive B cell receptors and anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis, were all substantially N-glycosylated in the fragment antigen-binding (Fab) domain. We observed that synovial macrophages and dendritic cells (DCs) as antigen-presenting cells (APC) that express MHC class II molecules have different glycan processing enzymes between RA and OA patient samples from sequencing analysis. Regulation of APC cellular process may be altered due to aberrant changes in TMEM230 expression (Supplementary Table). It is unclear how the changes in glycan composition establishes differences in immune reaction and will be investigated further.

Published studies also showed that RA was associated with reduction of cell-surface sialylation of synovial fibroblasts, promoting a cytokine-induced switch towards a pro-inflammatory phenotype. Our sequencing analysis shows that both immune cells, macrophages and fibroblast cells were associated with altered expression of glycan synthesizing and processing enzymes, but how these enzymes contribute to previously observed glycan composition in these diverse cell types will need to be further investigated.

5.7 | Possible Role of TMEM230 in Disease Determinations of RA Compared to OA

RA is an autoimmune disease that affects various tissues but predominantly is manifested in joints [9, 25, 34, 36, 78, 95, 96, 99–101].

Antibody glycosylation appears different in RA as compared to control patients with OA. Glycosylation changes in serum or plasma immunoglobulin G (IgG) for RA patients is predominantly described in the literature, certain studies have supported that glycosylation changes observed for immunoglobulin A (IgA) and total serum N-glycome composition are supportive that RA is a disease of chronic and systemic inflammation in contrast to injury induced localized inflammation in OA patients, as supported by our sequencing analysis. Our analyses also support that in contrast to OA, since different glycosylation signatures were observed in nonimmune system cells, the RA disease mechanism may in part be independent of the autoantibody status (Supplementary Table 1). For instance, we demonstrated that TMEM230 also regulates tissue remodeling by regulating secretion of EVs and granulation that may have a role in phagocytic cell (MLC and FSL) induced destructive remodeling. Granulation tissue at the edges of the synovial lining and extensive angiogenesis is also indicated as regulated by TMEM230 in phagocytic cells. Other TMEM230 mediated cell hallmarks identified by our studies have been demonstrated in MLC and FLS cells RA, such as reduced apoptosis, increased migratory invasive potential, reprogrammed cellular metabolism especially mitochondria.

Possible therapeutic methods for modulating TMEM230 at the mRNA and protein level for mitigating symptoms or onset of autoimmunity or cancer have been previously outlined by our group (EU Patent EP18707150.1, 2022-09-06 and US Patent US11566070B2, granted on 2023-01-31). We investigated the main types of RNA therapeutics for potential preclinical and clinical applications. Modulation of mRNA expression of TMEM230 by mRNA, antisense, RNA interference and RNA aptamers can be performed using long-term stabilized oligo molecules and lentiviral approach (as described in this study). Potentially, mRNA-based therapies may be coupled with vaccine development or with membrane bound vesicles for delivery of RNA therapies to patients, or for tissue specific targeting. Target gene therapy using antibodies is not possible due to TMEM230 being an intracellular cellular organelle bound transmembrane protein.

5.8 | Limitations in Studying the Expression Profiles of Glycan Processing Enzymes by Single Cell Sequencing Analysis

Glycoconjugates such as glycoproteins can be studied indirectly by sequencing of mRNA but “glycomodifications” are post transcriptional and largely posttranslational modifications that cannot be detected by sequencing. While we have manipulated expression of TMEM230 using human derived cell lines and primary blood vessel forming endothelial cells, as our conclusions from sequencing analysis are derived from using patient whole tissue (RA, OA, and GBM), further studies need to be done manipulating TMEM230 expression using patient derived cells to generate 3D organoids and co-cultures assays to validate our and conclusions [37]. A significant limitation of our study is also due to the fact we have analyzed mRNA levels from sequencing analysis that do not necessarily reflect the behavior of proteins that are conjugated to glycans. Glycosylation and glycoconjugate modifications are post

transcription and post-translation processes. As we described in this study these processes are not genetically coded and may in fact have a significant randomness associated with them. Therefore, an indirect approach to study noncoding and random events associated with glycan synthesis is to identify protein coding enzymes (hydrolases and transferases) that have a role in glycosylation using single cell sequencing. While single cell sequencing of all different cell types in a tissue may provide insight into the random behavior of the effects of glycan processing enzymes further research will require characterizing at the biochemical level the glycan composition of the candidate glycoproteins identified modulated by TMEM230.

6 | Conclusion

TMEM230 expression level alters the expression of enzymes that have a role in glycosylation and generates unique proteoglycan signatures in autoimmunity and cancer through its role as an ER membrane protein and as a primary component in intracellular trafficking and secretion of glycan factors and glycoconjugates that are cargo of vesicles. Glycan structures as secondary gene products are not encoded directly in the genome. A few percent of known genes in the human genome are enzymes and transporters responsible for the biosynthesis and assembly of glycans. We present novel data using single cell sequencing that supports that N-linked (GlcNAc) glycosylation is regulated by the endoplasmic reticulum membrane protein TMEM230. Aberrant expression of TMEM230 may contribute to autoimmunity and cancer development through its role in regulating components of N-linked (GlcNAc) glycosylation in cells of the innate and adaptive immune system. TMEM230 expression level modulation may be used for inhibiting destructive tissue remodeling in cancer and autoimmunity. We previously demonstrated destructive tissue remodeling to be induced by vascular mimicry or by aberrant blood vessel formation or by the possibility of renormalizing “leaky blood vessels” that are generated in tumors. Our current study suggests that TMEM230 in the ER initiates the earliest steps of glycan synthesis and glycosylation for endomembrane system dependent glycoconjugate sorting, trafficking, and secretion and may link the innate with the adaptive immune system in autoimmunity and cancer. Future studies on the role of TMEM230 across different types of autoimmune diseases or cancers will provide further insight to the potential applicability of TMEM230 as a therapeutic target and confirm its efficacy in clinical settings.

Author Contributions

Rolland A. Reinbold and Ileana Zucchi designed all experiments and outline of research and wrote the manuscript and validated all experimental results. Elena Angeli and Alberto Diaspro performed all microscopic imaging and contributed to writing. Edoardo Abeni performed all transcriptomic analysis. Cinzia Cocola performed immunostaining, all experiments and contributed to writing. Mira Palizban, Eleonora Piscitelli, Paride Pelucchi, Luca Lerma, Alice Chiodi, Cristiana Balbino, Martin Götze contributed concepts and reagents.

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Conflicts of Interest

Ileana Zucchi and Rolland Reinbold are recipients of EU Patent EP18707150.1, 2022-09-06 and US Patent US11566070B2, granted on 2023-01-31.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Glyco-Enzyme Repository database <http://glycoenzymes.ccruc.org> at <http://glycoenzymes.ccruc.edu>.

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Supporting Information

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